

THE USE OF PIDGIN-ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS AN EXPRESSION TOOL IN MUSIC TEXT WRITING

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Abstract

The article focuses on the use of pidgin English as an expressive tool in music text writing. Many musicians across the 36 states in Nigeria both, gospel, contemporary, art, popular and traditional employ the use of pidgin English in texts writing (although traditional musicians add a blend of their dialect and pidgin English etc.). The article seeks to shed light on this communication method in Nigeria and the reason musicians adopt the use in their textual writing. To achieve the objective of the article, the article relies on the texts of selected musicians/composers across Nigeria who employed the use of pidgin English as the primary source while the secondary source is from various media sources and journals. Stemming from the analysis of the various lyrical content, musicians/composers use pidgin as a linguistic flexibility to bridge ethnic divides and create national identity through songs thereby reaching a wider social stratum locally, nationally, and internationally. The use of pidgin English functions not merely as a means but also as a medium for social commentary, cultural

preservations and global marketing strategy. Finally, the use of Pidgin English by musicians/composers, creates a global aesthetics and artistic flare that mixes both local and global influences. Therefore, the services of musicians/composer can be employed by the government to use this expressive device (Pidgin English) to address issues of national interest.

Keywords: Language, Pidgin English, Text Writing, Music

Introduction

Ataisi & Nuwa (2022:37) states that music is an outlet of expression. Now, the question is, who expresses what? expression of what? What mode or medium would be used for the expression? To whom is the expression? Simply put, the first question addresses the writer (composer or musician), the second question addresses the idea to be expressed, the third question addresses the mode/medium of expressing the idea and the fourth question addresses the recipient. This implies that musicians have been using music as an outlet of their musical expression. This musical expression may be instrumental, vocal or both.

In vocal musical expression texts are used. In a broader spectrum, song texts writing has been used to address many issues regarding the polity by composers/song writers. Song texts refer to written lyrics or words in form of poems, figurative statements, phrases and or sentences either long or short involving the use of part of speech such as noun, pronoun, verb, adverb, adjectives etc., employed by composers/song writers. For the mode or medium of expression, many Nigerian musicians or composers uses the Nigerian Pidgin English as their medium of expression of communication. Pidgin English language is a derivation from the standard form of the English language. Ayodabo (2015:7) cites Onwudinjo (2007) that Pidgin springs from the template of the grammar, syntax, idioms, and semantics of African languages, especially West African. As such, it is naturally suited to nourish and express the African thought patterns without adulteration.

It is best suited to retain the open-mouthed laughter, the throbbing drums, the alluring dances, the proverbs, the ancestral spirits, the folktales. He further added that the capability of Pidgin to command enormous public appeal because of its spread, flexibility and the creative possibilities have made it yield creative possibilities), the second question addresses the idea to be expressed, the third question addresses the mode/medium of expressing the idea and the fourth question addresses the recipient.

Pidgin English is one of the lingua franca used in Nigeria for easy communication flow among Nigerians. Pidgin English is like the second native language before the Queen's English in Nigeria because irrespective of ethnic background pidgin

English is one language that can be used for easy communication for any purpose ranging from buying and selling and passing on of vital information. This method of communication is also the reason why some Nigerian artistes employ the use of Pidgin English in writing their song texts. Commenting on the usage of pidgin English in Nigeria Olatunji (2001) explains that pidgin English is the label for the jargon consisting chiefly of English words, often corrupted in pronunciation, which is used for inter-communication between different ethnic groups in Nigeria.

Olatunji (2001) further state that Pidgin has been with us since the colonial era that pidgin has always been regarded as the unofficial language of the ‘uneducated’, The pluralistic nature of Nigeria consisting as it does of hundreds of ethnic groups with different languages has aided the development of Pidgin English as a popular language in Nigeria and that many popular musicians have used it in their composition and performances to be able to reach a wide audience. He also noted that a study of music in Nigeria shows that the most popular musicians are those who infuse pidgin English into their songs. Corroborating Olatunji’s assertion on the use of pidgin English language as a communicative medium, the paper summarize that many Nigerian music writers/composers of various music genre, style, and type have used pidgin English in passing on their musical ideas to a very wide range of audience even across Nigeria borders to global audiences through music’s sound matrix and song texts writing.

What is behind this method of communication? The answer lies in the fact that in Nigeria, after the mother tongue, the next language of communication is pidgin English. Secondly, for music business purpose, musicians target a large array of audience across Nigeria to get more sales and thirdly for ease of message decoding to a large extent. What is the essence of passing on information, if not for proper decoding of such information, therefore, it is imperative that method of communication or of passing on information should be considered by communicators and music writers in order to get the targeted objective of the message. Although the paper is not centered on the most popular musician or art music nor infusion of pidgin English in text writing, it is concurred that pidgin English has been key to passing on of messages understood by many Nigerians irrespective of ethnic divide which is the end product of any communicative process. It has been established that Pidgin English used in music texts writing reaches a wider range of audience in terms of message communication and appeal. Furthermore, pidgin English language in today’s contemporary world most especially in Nigeria is not restricted to the ‘uneducated’ as stated by Olatunji (2001) in his assertions. Today, both the ‘educated’ and ‘uneducated’ speaks pidgin English language. It is arguable that in Nigeria, pidgin English language usage in music texts compositions has a greater number of audience/listeners. The paper

samples some music writers/composers of various genre and bring to roost the ideas of the paper.

Methodology

The paper employs a qualitative descriptive approach by gathering lyrical samples from individuals, digital repositories of selected musicians and audio tracks.

Theoretical Framework

Although various theories like domain theory based on Joshua Fishman’s Domain Analysis, Leech’s Categories of Meaning, Code-Switching and Code-Mixing exists, the paper employs Creolization theory which posits that cultural forms emerges from intense contact which often creates new, hybrid entities with their own structural integrity.

Selected Song Texts in Pidgin English Language

Ataisi & Nuwa (2022) submits that the use of language is unavoidable in every activity of man. Language is used when man is active and inactive. Using language for expression is one of the communicative roles of language. Language is the raw material of music as it is used by artistes for expression. The social realities of a culture have bearings on the language of musicians as they use language to communicate to the society (p.37). Pidgin language makes use of lexis from English languages such as To, Go, Unless, Tell, You, Am, to mention a few. Pidgin English cut across Nigeria as a country which makes it easy for Nigerians to communicate effectively with one another from different tribes and background. Ohwonohwo & Chiedu (2021:1) affirms that in Nigeria, Pidgin English is used to communicate effectively, it is a language which everybody speaks in Nigeria, the Pidgin language has become extensive, it is now often used in musical industry. This is corroborated by Mbachaga (2010) that music is a fundamental phenomenon that permeates all aspects of the Nigerian society and the use of pidgin lyrics as a linguistic style of expression to captivate the audience and communicate certain realities in the society is not a new phenomenon. Table showing selected song title, language, genre and composer/song writer/performer. Also, the first five songs namely Puff and Pass, Our Leaders, Defender, Diana and Zombi were briefly analysed respectively.

S/N	SONG TITLE	LANGUAGE	GENRE	COMPOSER
1.	PUFF AND PASS	PIDGIN	HIP-POP	SHALLIPOPI AND ZERRY DL
2.	OUR LEADERS	PIDGIN	ART	E. J. OKAFOR
3.	DEFENDER	PIDGIN	GOSPEL	FRANK EDWARDS

4.	DIANA	PIDGIN	HIP-POP	DADDY SHOWKEY
5.	ZOMBI	PIDGIN	AFRO	FELA ANIKULAKPO
6.	YELLOW SISI	PIDGIN	HIGHLIFE	KOFI SAMMY
7.	GENTLEMAN	PIDGIN	AFRO	FELA ANIKULAKPO8.
8.	IF I KNOW SAY	PIDGIN	HIGH LIFE	SALLY YOUNG
9.	WE GO SURVIVE O	PIDGIN	ART	E. J. OKAFOR
10.	SO MY BROTHER	PIDGIN	HIGHLIFE	REX LAWSON

Song Title 1: Puff and Pass by Shallipopi and Zerry DL

Bee, beezy

Say wara, wara

They call me Shallipopi

Bee

My men dey surprise (eh)

The way I dey puff am, dey puff am dey pass

(Dey puff am dey pass) (confirm)

The way e dey kpo, e dey blast

(dey puff am dey pass)

Bring ray loud make I surfree dray (eh)

Way too much talking e no dey shout

Kpekpo dey there, my squad on guard, oh (dey on guard, oh, dey on guard)

Steady bobby like a soldier for Afghanistan (eh)

I eat you but not a cannibal

Dem dey rush like an animal (Animal, animal, animal)

Big life we surfree mount cartel (wahala)

Say

Puff puff pass, and mix am with martel (wahala)

Big man life we surfree mount cartel (wahala say)

Puff puff pass, and mix am with martel
Pass am
(Bololo) puff am, e don cast, e don cast
(Bololo) puff am, (bololo) pass am E don burst (wahala)
E don cast (eh) (olo) puff am (bololo) pass am
E don cast, e don cast
Puff am, pass am
E don cast, e don cast (nagodey) puff am, pass am
E don burst, e don cast
Eko fit make you kolo
Eh, the way you blow blow (nagodey)
I cause you go sell your kolo

Source: <https://genius.com>

Brief Analysis

The text has some element of rhyme: example Bee; beezy; kpo; blast; cartel; martel; burst, cast; Eko, kolo; The lyrics has lots of rhyming techniques and repetition including figurative sentences. For instance, ‘e don cast’ is a pidgin expression that signifies being caught, a failed plan or when a secret is out in the open – usually associated to negative attitude. ‘Dem dey rush like an animal’ is a simili. The phrase describes people who are scrambling or hurrying without order, patience or civilized behaviour.

Song Title 2: Our Leaders by Enoch J. Okafor

Our leaders, una help us
Our leaders, make una listen to our cry
Our leaders, una hear us
Our leaders, una listen to our cry
Who go save us from this monster?
Who go save us from this monster?
Who go save us from this monster?
This monster wen won destroy our future

Who go save us from this hunger?
Who go save us from this hunger?
Who go save us from this hunger?
This hunger wen won take over our land
Our leaders, una help us
Our leaders, make una listen to our cry
Our leaders, una hear us
Our leaders, una listen to our cry

Source: Enoch J. Okafor

Brief Analysis

‘Our leaders una help us’ is a lyric in pidgin English referring to the masses’ request/plea for assistance, intervention or betterer governance from government officials, leaders in communities or bosses usually a plea born out of frustration or desperation, a cry for mercy due to hardship. ‘Who go save us from this monster?’ – depending on the context of usage, this is a rhetorical question depicting an expression of despair. It is an expression that describes a situation, person, or system that has become oppressive, destructive or monstrous.

Song Title 3: Defender by Frank Edwards

Defender
Na you be my defender
I go sing my song you go raise my music
Oh nanana nene, defender
Them say with your name I no go sell my music
I tell am say why I no go call my Jesus
But everywhere them don dey play my music o e e
Na you be my defender
Your love for me still dey make me wonder
Hale hale glory glory to your name
Everyday na you dey mark me correct O baba
Na you be my defender

From glory to glory
You don change my story oh
Goodness and mercy dey follow me o
Na the thing wey my God dey do
Na you cover me, cover me, cover me
From when I was a little boy, baba
Na you be my defender
My love for you dem no dey talk am finish
When dem gather na you dey scatter them

Source: Musixmatch

Brief Analysis

‘Na you be my defender’ literally means you are my protector or the one who protects me depending on the context of usage. In Christian setting, it is a declaration that God is the ultimate protector. ‘Your love for me still dey make me wonder’ is an expression of deep gratitude and surprise at the intensity or consistency of someone’s affection, in this case, God’s affection. ‘You don change my story oh’ is a pidgin English expression which means that someone’s status in life has been greatly improved for instance from poverty to wealth.

Song Title 4: Diana by Daddy Showkey

Why u dey cry clean your face
Godstime is the best
God go give you your own
If you see my mama hossana
Tell am say o hossana
I dey for ghetto hossana
If you see my mama hossana
Tell am say o hossana
I dey for ghetto hossana
I no get problem hossana
He get one woman hossana
Her name na Diana hossana

Oh Diana baby hossana
Oh Diana baby hossana
I say she fine well well hossana
Oh Diana baby hossana
Oh Diana baby hossana
Diana stay for husband house (hossana)
For good nine years (hossana)
Diana love bobby oh hossana
Husband mama come hossana
Diana pack your load hossana
Diana pack your load hossana
Husband people come hossana
All the way from village hossana
They marry this wife hossana
For Diana husband hossana
If you see my mama hossana
Tell am say o hossana
I dey for ghetto hossana
I no get problem hossana
I no get problem hossana
Source: Musixmatch

Brief Analysis

‘Why u dey cry clean your face’ this is an expression the encourages a person to move past a painful situation instead of wallowing in self-pity. It literally means don’t let this get to you. ‘I no get problem’ on the other hand, expresses a relaxed mood or bring able to live a stress free life and easy accommodation of others.

Song Title 5: Zombi by Fela Anikulakpo

Zombie o, zombie (Zombie o, zombie)
Zombie o, zombie (Zombie o, zombie)
Zombie no go go, unless you tell am to go (Zombie)

Zombie no go stop, unless you tell am to stop (Zombie)
Zombie no go turn, unless you tell am to turn (Zombie)
Zombie no go think, unless you tell am to think (Zombie)
Zombie o, zombie (Zombie o, zombie)
Zombie o, zombie (Zombie o, zombie)
Zombie no go go, unless you tell am to go (Zombie)
Zombie no go stop, unless you tell am to stop (Zombie)
Zombie no go turn, unless you tell am to turn (Zombie)
Zombie no go think, unless you tell am to think (Zombie)
Zombie o, zombie (Zombie o, zombie)
Zombie o, zombie (Zombie o, zombie)
Tell them to go straight, na joro, jara, joro
No break, no gear, no sense, joro jara, joro
Tell them to go kill, na joro, jara, joro
No break, no gear, no sense, joro jara, joro
Tell them to go quench, na joro, jara, joro
No break, no gear, no sense, joro jara, joro
Go and kill (joro, jaro, joro)
Go and die (joro, jaro, joro)
Go and quench (joro, jaro, joro)
Put am for reverse! (joro, jaro, joro)
Go and quench (joro, jaro, joro)
Go and kill (joro, jaro, joro)
Go and die (joro, jaro, joro)
Put am for reverse! (joro, jaro, joro)
Go and die (joro, jaro, joro)
Go and quench (joro, jaro, joro)
Go and kill (joro, jaro, joro)
Put am for reverse! (joro, jaro, joro)

Source: <https://genius.com>

Brief Analysis

‘Zombie o, zombie’ this expression is a scathing metaphor for blind obedience, in the this context to mock and criticize the Nigerian military. ‘Zombie no go go, unless you tell am to go’ depicts lack of independent thought reflecting a total surrender to a superiors’ will.

Song Title 6: Yellow Sisi by Kofi Sammy

Haa, haa, haaa, haaa, haaa, haaa, haaa, haaa, wonderful

Listen, I go talk am

I don talk am before,

But now I go repeat am

Because dey advice you, you hear?

Yellow sisi dey for corner

Putting hand for jaw

Wetin dey course am oooo - eh

Money palava – eh

Hay, you see-am?

Yellow sisi dey for corner

Putting hand for jaw

Wetin dey course am oooo - eh

Money palava – eh

Yellow, Yellow Yellow Yellow – eh

Yellow sisterah

Wetin course oooo – eh

Money palavaah

Why? no papa nor dey hear pikin – o

Pikin nor dey hear papa o

Everything just dey make yajaaa, for this world, e good? No.

Yellow, Yellow Yellow Yellow – eh

Yellow sisterah

Wetin dey course oooo – eh
Money palavaeh
There is no hurry in life
Yellow sister you just stay calm
Make you nor wound yourself
Because if I hold you
Money go quench you
Yellow sisi dey for corner
Putting hand for jaw
Wetin dey course am oooo - eh
Money palava – aa
Yellow sisi dey for corner -ah...
Putting hand for jaw
Wetin dey course am oooo - eh
Money palava – aa
E eh, See something
My pikin wen I don train finish
Look am, na e dey for corner put hand for jaw
If you ask say wetin
E say na money, na wa-oooh
Now, yellow sisi don comot for corner
E dey for highway
Dey wait for moto wen e dey pass
From house to house
E good? Noo.
Yellow, Yellow Yellow Yellow – eh
Yellow sisterah
Wetin dey course oooo – eh
Money palavaeh

Stop walking from place to place because of money

Yellow, Yellow Yellow Yellow – eh

Yellow sisterah

Wetin dey course oooo – eh

Money palavaeh

There is no hurry in life

Yellow sister you just stay calm

Make you nor wound yourself

Because if I hold you

Money go quench you

Yellow sisi dey for corner

Putting hand for jaw

Wetin dey course am oooo - eh

Money palava – aa

Yellow sisi dey for corner -ah...

Putting hand for jaw

Wetin dey course am oooo - eh

Money palava – aa

I go die – oo

Make you nor die

U go killi me

Wayo wayo na-a (small small na-a)

Na you like am so?

Pikin wen nor gree make e mama sleep na so,

Why you dey say, wayo, wayo (small small)

Nor be money you dey find?

You go die

You get e money go home I beg

Yellow sisi e don do for you go home

Use the money wen you get
Go home na-a-a
This December you nor go, go home
Hurry You small girl
Go home
Yellow sisi dey for corner
Putting hand for jaw
Wetin dey course am oooo - eh
Money palava – aa
Yellow sisi dey for corner
Putting hand for jaw
Wetin dey course am oooo - eh
Money palava – aa

Source: <https://rogersallstarrecords>

Song Title 7: Gentleman by Fela Anikulapku

I no be gentleman at all
I no be gentleman at all
I no be gentleman at all oh
I no be gentleman at all, at all

I be African man, original
(I no be gentleman at all oh)
I be African man, original
(I no be gentleman at all oh)

I no be gentleman at all
I no be gentleman at all
I no be gentleman at all oh

I no be gentleman at all, at all

I be African man, original

(I no be gentleman at all oh)

I be African man, original

(I no be gentleman at all oh)

And the horns they blow

Source: MusixMatch

Song Title 8: If I Know Say by Sally Young (an excerpt)

If I know say na so the world go be o

Na two head I for bring o

If I know say na so the world go be o

Na two head I for bring o

When you do wrong

The world say you do wrong o

When you do right,

The world say you do right;

Na wetin I go do when world people go praise me

Source: Apple Music

Song Title 9: We Go Survive o by Enoch J. Okafor

We go survive o

We go survive o

We go survive o

We go survive o

No matter how the country be

We go survive o

No matter how the country be

We go survive o

We go survive o mama

We go survive o
We go survive o papa
We go survive o
No matter how the country be
We go survive o
No matter how the country be
We go survive o

Source: E .J. Okafor

Song Title 10: Oh My Son by Rex Lawson

Oh my Son,
You should be ready
To lay good foundation,
Earlier the better
In the nearest future
You will be one of the leaders
So we pray
Amen
Oh my daughter,
You should be ready
To lay good foundation,
Earlier the better
In the nearest future
You will be one of the leaders
So we pray
Amen
To become a leader
Is not very easy
To become a man

Is not a day work
Everybody ambition,
Is to become a leader
Is to become a big man
That is the struggle
So my Son
You should be ready
To lay good foundation
Earlier the better
In the nearest future
You will be one of the leaders
So we pray
Amen
Oh my brother
You should be ready
To lay good foundation
Earlier the better
In the nearest future
You will be one of the leaders
So we pray
Amen
Oh my daughter,
You should be ready
To lay good foundation,
Earlier the better
In the nearest future
You will be one of the leaders
So we pray
Amen

To become a leader
Is not very easy
To become a man
Is not a day work
Everybody ambition,
Is to become a leader
Is to become a big man
That is the struggle
So my daughter
You should be ready
To lay good foundation
Earlier the better
In the nearest future
You will be one of the leaders
So we pray
Amen
To become a leader
Is not very easy
To become a man
Is not a day work
Everybody's ambition,
Is to become a leader
Is to become a big man
That is the struggle
So my Son
You should be ready
To lay good foundation
Earlier the better
In the nearest future

You will be one of the leaders

So we pray

Amen

So we pray

Amen

So my daughter

You should be ready

To lay good foundation

Earlier the better

In the nearest future

You will be one of the leaders

So we pray

Amen

To become a leader

Is not very easy

To become a man

Is not a day work

Everybody's ambition,

Is to become a leader

Is to become a big man

That is the struggle

So my daughter

You should be ready

To lay good foundation

Earlier the better

In the nearest future

You will be one of the leaders

So we pray

Amen

Oh my daughter
You should be ready
To lay good foundation
Earlier the better
In the nearest future
You will be one of the leaders
So we pray
Amen

Source: facebook

All the genre of song texts or lyrics chronicled above dealt with different themes addressing different situation and aspects of the society; some dealt on moral issues, hard work, political issues, economic issues, issues on self-esteem, courage, self-reliant, leadership issues, patience, stereotype, obedience, self-determination and actualization. The lyrics ‘the world say you do wrong o’ is an expression in pidgin English. The lyrics in its entirety touches on the vanity of life, the regret and the unpredictability of life. It cautions people on how to make right choices and torches on morality and the inevitability of death.

Conclusion

The article highlights the use of pidgin English as an expressive tool in music text writing by many musicians and music composers across the 36 states in Nigeria. The article also enunciates the reason musicians adopt the use of pidgin English in their textual writing. In addition, the messages inherent addresses various topics/themes in the society. Finally, it is imperative to add that in contemporary times, the exigence of cogent, vivid and informative music text writing is a clarion call to all music composers/song writers irrespective of language medium opted for that would stand the test of time.

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